

ISic3068

I.Sicily inscription 3068

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

tomb 50, necropolis near Scala Greca

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 17032

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332227

1. [— — — —]
2. ΑΚΕ. [— —]
3. Κάλλ[ων]-
4. ος τόδ [ε]
5. σῆμ[α π]-
6. ερίφρ[ον]-
7. ος ἦν [υσε]
8. μ ἦ,τ [ηρ].
- 9.

Edition: PHI336195

1. Ἄκε σ [ία(?) τοῦ]
2. Καλλ[ικράτε]-
3. ος τόδ [ε καλὸν(?)]
4. σῆμ [α — — —]
5. Ἐριφρ[άδε]-

6. ος ἢ μ [έδουσα(?)]

7. μήτ[ηρ έποίη].

8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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